

CYBER SECURITY OF THE INTERNET OF THINGS IoT

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Abstract. *The article presents the scientific novelty and the main problems of cybersecurity in the IoT Internet of Things. Vulnerable devices that may be at risk are listed. Methods are shown on how you can protect yourself using a VPN network, the role of artificial intelligence, and the vulnerability of IP addresses. As well as real-life examples.*

Keywords: *internet of things, cybersecurity, risks, VPN, 3d printers, smart TV, NASA admin, VPN routers.*

The scientific novelty of the cyber security of the Internet of Things (IoT) is the processes occurring in sensor, computer and telecommunication networks. IoT cyber security is a technology segment devoted to protecting linked devices and networks in the Internet of things (IoT). IoT entails connecting a system of interconnected computing devices, mechanical and digital machinery, items, animals, and/or people to the Internet. Each "thing" is given a unique identifier and the capacity to transport data autonomously across a network. Allowing devices to connect to the Internet exposes them to several major risks if not adequately secured.

The Internet of Things connects various objects and devices via the internet to communicate with similarly connected devices or machines. With an internet connection, consumers can now purchase a wide range of products, from automobiles to refrigerators. By extending networking capabilities to all aspects of our lives, we can become more efficient, save time and money, and have access to our digital lives whenever we need it. Cybersecurity professionals frequently refer to this fact as increasing the attack surface that hackers can exploit. Security professionals are aware of this and work to manage the resulting security risks. To know more about it, check out best Cyber security Certification programs [1-3].

The Internet of Things is closely related to artificial intelligence (AI) systems and devices that communicate with each other. The risks associated with smart devices can be divided into two groups. The first is software failure, where you can be taken out of service due to a defective or damaged device. The second group involves the impact of hacker attacks and malicious viruses on the IoT device.

The first problem is internal and can be solved with regular device maintenance, but the second, external problem requires you to consider the security measures, of which a good VPN is a must, as a reliable means to ensure your individual safety on the Internet. Luckily, premium VPN providers like Le VPN provide the ability to protect all your devices, including those in your home, from all sorts of intrusions.

The Internet of Things (IoT - Internet of Things) is a term that characterizes the process of interaction of intelligent devices and devices that are already present and regularly added to our daily lives. These devices are usually connected to the Internet, they do not even communicate with people, but more often with other devices and software, both in the home and on the Web. The size, complexity, and cybersecurity of these systems is highly dependent on the number of interconnected devices you have in your home, as well as the type and generation of those devices. In some cases, an IoT system is simply a peripheral device that sits in an office or home office.

Printers and scanners were one of the first representatives of the IoT, which are now ubiquitous both at home and at work.

IoT risks and cybersecurity

The main risk of IoT devices is that they can communicate with each other without our knowledge. Of course, this seems to save our efforts and time, but this state of affairs is associated with a wide range of risks. The best analogy for the risks associated with the Internet of Things is kindergarten, where all your devices are toddlers. The only difference is that the IoT has not yet developed the instinct of self-preservation in the way that human cubs have. If you leave your child in the company of other children without adult supervision, you will have free time to do other things or focus on your main job. But we all understand that this is a huge risk that children constantly need to be monitored and protected. We must be sure that their time together is safe for them and for us. If you leave your IoT devices unattended and don't babysit a VPN and an antivirus system, chances are that a "stranger uncle" will come along and pretend to be your friend and steal or damage one of your devices [4,5].

Devices: uses and risks

Regardless of their type, the biggest cybersecurity risk is always devices with limited security features that are directly connected to the Internet or are part of a system that is not properly cyber-secured. You can try to outsource the VPN server to a company, however, if cybersecurity is not a priority for that company, then most likely there are not many qualified IT security specialists there, and the protection technologies used may be outdated and in need of updating. One example of the risks associated with the IoT was the hacking of more than 50,000 printers during the competition between Pewdiepie and T-Series YouTube channels for first place among subscribers when a popular Swedish blogger tried to keep his channel in first place.

While using a good VPN would solve most of the problems associated with IoT devices, some VPN providers, such as Le VPN, have begun to offer their customers additional options that are necessary to protect many high-tech devices and which provide individual cyber security. Phones and tablets are not considered IoT devices, because it is considered that with the help of these devices we ourselves communicate. Thus, a false impression is created that we personally control the process.

The biggest risk for IoT devices is the real-time data exchange that happens all the time. That is why smartphones immediately fall into the risk group - they are constantly updating something, downloading and unloading, every user knows about it. Whether it's communicating with apps, services, or some other database, your phone's security is constantly at risk. However, some vulnerabilities, especially those related to the protection of personal data, can be fixed using only a VPN, but many others require additional steps. While most smartphone app marketplaces make sure that their digital products are cyber-secure (because they are required by law), almost every smartphone owner has downloaded some unverified third-party app at least once. As a rule, any application is considered insecure if it was obtained from an untrusted source. Giving such an app permission to send and receive all your data, as well as view and use your phone contacts and media content, is essentially giving you permission to hack you and put your phone at the mercy of the app developer.

Peripherals and Tools

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These IoT devices include those that connect to the Internet themselves, but do not have a system that we, the owners of the devices, can easily access. Technically, your printers and scanners have an operating system that controls them, but accessing the files on that system and somehow modifying them is very difficult. Thus, you cannot control the cyber security of these devices. The best way to solve this problem is to install a VPN router and use it to secure all devices that connect via WiFi.

Printers are the most common type of IoT device. Before the advent of wireless printers, which today can print pictures sent from a phone from anywhere in the world, printers were connected to computers that were connected to the Internet and could share their printer access with other devices. The main security risk here is usually that the printer does not have any kind of password to prevent hackers from gaining control of it. If the person trying to hack you know your IP address, they can guess the address of the printer and gain full access to it. When it comes to security risks, 3D printers are very similar to their regular 2D counterpart. The main difference lies only in the amount of memory and processing power of these printers [6,7].

Large memory and a fast processor mean that a malicious application or file can be stored and executed invisibly, without any noticeable sign when the device is running.

Household robots. Roomba is far from the only one, but probably the most famous household robot that many people have at home. This cute little disc-shaped vacuum cleaner can do its own cleaning and is very popular with housewives. You may not have known, but the little Roomba packs a lot of processing power. The small Qualcomm chip in the new version of the robot is about 30% stronger than the entire computing power of NASA's 1969 mission to the moon.

Although Roomba or any other household robot will not store your sensitive data, it can become a carrier of malware. Also, while there have been no confirmed cases so far, if an attacker hacks into your vacuum cleaner, they will be able to scan the layout of your apartment.

Virtual assistants. Having an artificial intelligence virtual assistant is not bad in itself. In time, we will certainly see a significant development of this intelligence, provided that it is given the opportunity to learn. But, when you want to ensure your own cyber security, you will find that Siri, Alexa, Cortana, and Bixby are the weakest links in your house. These devices are designed to serve people, they respond to any voice and are ready to work with different users. If you're not secure with a VPN and don't use two-factor authentication for important commands like online shopping or streaming subscriptions, your virtual assistant can be the source of multiple data breaches.

Appliances. Any savvy cybersecurity expert will never tell you that cybersecurity features for refrigerators, ovens, and microwaves are being developed somewhere and by someone. If you hear this, know that it is either a fantasy or a lie. Unfortunately, these devices can store an incredible amount of our personal data, posing serious risks to the Internet of Things and making them a regular target for hackers and data thieves.

Smart refrigerators and food processors. The benefits of IoT when using kitchen appliances are clear. From remote access to oven controls when you're not at home, to ordering groceries online the moment you realize your fridge is running out of food. The biggest risk for these devices is the exact personal data that IoT devices use to complete your task. To order food through the refrigerator with a single click, you will need to re-enter all your credit card details, as well as your name and home address.

In order to ensure your cyber security in this case, the device must be connected to a VPN router that will reliably hide your IP address from anyone who tries to intercept the connection. In addition, online purchases should only be made in stores that guarantee your privacy and security. Finally, it would be nice to have an alternative bank card to pay for your online purchases through IoT devices, as well as two-factor verification when making such purchases. Television systems Smart TV. The cyber security of smart TV systems depends a lot on how you use your TV. Even the best VPN for Firestick, Roku, or similar services won't protect you from data collection by Xbox during a live stream. While the TV itself doesn't contain a lot of your personal data, the security vulnerability comes from being linked to a game console, where there's a lot more of that data. Connecting a TV to a VPN improves cybersecurity by preventing many of the problems associated with individual security, especially since some smart TVs already have built-in VPN services. However, if you're not careful, a hacker can gain access to your media system, wait for it to connect to your console, and then steal your personal information [8].

How can an attacker hack an IoT system?

Hacking something means tricking a device into pretending to be someone who has legitimate access to it. In the same way that a hacker will “make up stories” by talking to bored help desk employees in order to get the password for someone’s bank account, he will lie to your home IoT devices, convincing them that he has the right to control them. In addition, these devices are typically shared between multiple family members without any personal passwords, which is why the devices are so easily accessible and insecure.

If any intruder from the internet knows your home IP address, he may try to access the IP address of one of your devices. After connecting to your home system, it will test the addresses of the internal network until it finds a weak spot. By gaining access to just one device, a hacker can infect it with malware or control it until it connects to other home devices. In this way, it can gradually get to your personal, confidential, or banking data.

How to protect yourself with a VPN. Having a VPN is the best way to protect any device from intrusions, snooping, and other IoT risks. But to protect all your devices, you need a premium VPN provider that specializes in IoT technologies and provides intelligent security solutions for your home appliances, as well as mobile devices and personal computers. Le VPN solved this problem by developing a VPN router that can connect an almost infinite number of devices to a smart home VPN system. Combined with the regular VPN service plan, which covers up to five devices, wherever they are, this will keep your IoT secure for the foreseeable future. While a premium VPN has a full set of features that protect all IoT devices, its main advantage is anonymity. By using a VPN, you do not reveal you’re true IP address to anyone. Any hacker who obtains the IP address you show will have to hack into the VPN server instead of your home system. And if he does not call on the help of Elon Musk or Robert Lightfoot Jr., the chief administrator of NASA, then his whole life will not be enough to hack the VPN server. By blocking direct access to your devices, you can decide for yourself what information you are willing to voluntarily provide to companies that provide you with certain services.

Conclusion

Having smart home devices is one of the many benefits of living in the 21st century, and you certainly don't have to give up progress in order to keep your personal data safe. That being said, you should be aware of the threats associated with IoT in order to better protect yourself from

all sorts of intrusions. The best way to mitigate IoT risks is to connect all your devices to the internet through premium VPNs like Le VPN or use VPN routers to securely connect all devices in your home to the internet. Once you've secured your individual cybersecurity this way, you can sit back on the couch, tell Alexa to turn on your Smart TV and download a few episodes of Black Mirror to see the future of humankind thanks to the rapid development of artificial intelligence.

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